

THE IMPORTANCE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN IMPROVING THE IRC SYSTEM IN HIGHER MEDICAL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *Due to the most rapid technological development, globalization and integration processes, huge changes and problems in the world education system are becoming real problems of rapid technological changes in the whole world. In this article, I will analyze the systems of IRC (Information Resource Center) in the foreign state education system and make recommendations for improving electronic library systems. The relevance of information and resource centers in the development of our country, the policy of digitalization of the medical field, the creation of amenities for the population, the development of medicine using the world's advanced technologies, and the training of competitive personnel have a special place.*

Keywords: *information resource center, IRC systems, DSpace, open access, repository, research capital, archiving, digital technologies.*

I. INTRODUCTION

In the conditions of globalization, modern information technology is a tool that determines the strategy and tactics of the development of large libraries. The development of the world economy is directly dependent on the quality indicators of the comprehensive education system, and the level of knowledge and potential of highly educated personnel is an important factor in the innovative development of countries. Of course, in this situation, the role of the information resource center (IRC) system has the highest goal of educating a reader who has the ability to read independently, think, analyze, synthesize, make decisions, perfectly understand the ideas of national independence, and think about it independently.

All the laws and normative-regulatory documents related to the field of medical education envisage the development of the system of higher and secondary special education in our republic in accordance with world standards, bringing the quality of education to the level of international standards.

The purpose of the work under consideration is to study the directions of development, legal bases, management structure and characteristics and standards of the information-resource center system in the medical institution of higher education, to develop relevant conclusions and proposals based on them.

Achieving the set goal requires the following tasks:

- ensuring adaptation of the electronic form of information-library resources to changes in information and telecommunication technologies;
- ensuring connection to the network of electronic libraries of other information-library institutions;
- To study the features of IRC financing in the world medical higher education system, as well as the process of monitoring control;

- To open the doors of knowledge to major countries of the world for the institutions of the medical education system of the republic based on the learned experience;
- Preparation of conclusions and proposals for reforms of the republican medical education system based on the learned experience.

The object of the work is information resource centers in the medical higher education system, and the subject is to study the features of the DSPACE software in the information resource centers of the medical higher education system.

II. THE PROSPECT OF MODERN ICT IN IRC

The theoretical aspect of the subject is that in the conditions of globalization, information-resource centers of a number of large foreign libraries in the world (Great Britain, USA, France, Germany, Denmark, Finland, Japan, etc.) development of special programs in accordance with. These libraries have developed information infrastructure and telecommunication means. Among the new forms of service introduced in modern libraries, the following can be noted: delivery of bibliographic and textual information by means of telecommunications; providing analytical information about the content of the most requested periodicals, delivering information to users in any form that is most convenient for them (print, SD, Web, online); business information and hakoza.

The development trends of all medical higher education systems of the world are implemented on the basis of laws and are not limited by the laws of the nation-state. The global medical higher education system, such as the UK higher medical education system, is characterized by the composition, standards, and funding system of compulsory education, postgraduate education and training. It is important to study the directions of development in the 21st century. Similarly, it has its own direction of development in other countries of the world.

The globalization of the medical education space, ensuring the mobility of personnel, the development of international standards for the quality of medical education, the 21st century presents new tasks to the medical education system.

The introduction of information and communication technologies also requires new developments in the field of library space organization. IFLA (International Federation of Library Associations) has a special department called "Library Buildings and Equipment" which deals with issues such as design, construction, equipment of new buildings, organization of technological processes and services, decoration and use of the building. studies and summarizes the world experience in this direction.

It should be noted that initial steps are being taken to create a comprehensive concept of the organization of library buildings in the form of a complex of interrelated tasks. The conclusion that the library service directly depends on the quality of organization of the library building is important in principle.

Fundamental reforms in the field of medical education, using the positive experience of the IRC system of developed countries, will certainly bear fruit.

As a result of the comparative analysis of the development trends of the IRC system of foreign countries, it is of great practical importance to study the aspects of social economic development and formation of the leading countries. The experience of perfect production of IRC system standards and formation of uniform educational spaces is reflected in the European Union. Formation of the IRC system on the basis of uniform standards in a certain space provides a high

quality level of information resources users and their mobility and competition in a single educational space.

Currently, while IT technologies are developing exponentially, Meta and Big DATA systems are being created, and artificial intelligence is entering all fields, the content enrichment of information resource centers depends mainly on the intellectual potential of its specialists. , in this case, that is, the working specialist must be a strong specialist who can work with all techniques, not only able to work, but also well-educated. This specialist is able to understand the activities of the library, knows what information is, where to place it, in which database, knows the value and value of this information, can directly use computer programs, and if necessary, create a new algorithm and a program based on this algorithm. it is required to be a specialist with strong potential. The main goal of enriching the IRC information base is to enrich the "Intellectual" potential of students and youth. The organization of information-resource centers is an automated management system for the creation of a database necessary to increase that intellectual potential.

The development of IRC is based on the following important factors:

1. Technical support; 2. Software; 3. Information supply; 4. Staffing.

The main tasks of the IRC should be:

- based on the principle of providing the opportunity to choose the source, forms and methods of obtaining information using modern high-performance information and communication technologies, favorable conditions for comprehensively satisfying the intellectual, knowledge, spiritual, moral and cultural needs of the population, especially young people, and wide creating a database of information resources;

- to support the revival and further development of national culture and the preservation of the historical, spiritual and cultural heritage of its people;

- participation in the implementation of state policy in the field of information-library activities, development of proposals and recommendations on the main directions of further development of information-library institutions, taking into account the continuous improvement and increase of the level of information-library services to the population;

- organizational-methodical management of scientific-research and scientific-methodical work of information-library institutions, their coordination, within the framework of implementation of information-library activities, including effective interaction with them regarding the exchange and mutual use of information resources provide;

- improving the conditions, forms and methods of providing information-library services to the population, introducing special software complexes, creating electronic information-information services, automating the processes of information-library activities based on the use of modern computer tools and data transmission technologies provide;

- priority development of electronic services that provide users with remote access to information and library resources of information and library institutions, forming a collective electronic catalog of information and library institutions and an electronic information and library fund, connected to the database of leading foreign information resources, and conduct;

- Systematically replenishing the IRC fund with national and foreign publications, maintaining a state bibliographic account of publications, careful preservation of rare and particularly valuable publications, introducing modern methods of conservation and restoration of manuscript books and rare publications, promoting their reliable storage. organization of maintenance under the conditions of a special regime;

- continuous improvement of IRC's personnel capacity based on the selection of highly qualified specialists on the basis of competition, retraining of personnel of information-library institutions and establishment of a continuous system of improving their qualifications.

Today in Uzbekistan, several licensed information resources are used in the local library of the National Library. They are: Scopus, Web of science, EBSCO Academic, EBSCO Audio, eLibrary, JSTOR, Library Press Display, ProQuest, etc.

It is desirable to use the DSPACE repository software in optimizing the operation of the IRC system of higher medical education.

The DSpace electronic library platform was created together with the Hewlett-Packard company and the Federation of Universities created to implement the project.

All educational institutions and scientific research institutions in the world can download Dspace software free of charge from the Internet tIRCo and can adapt their policy according to the educational form of the institution in terms of scientific directions, because this software is an open source software. According to the OpenDOAR catalog data are divided into several types of institutional repositories

1. Software types of archives
2. Platforms of repositories

In the Tashkent Medical Academy (TTA), scientific articles, literature of all directions available in the IRC, dissertations and abstracts are placed on the Dspace repository platform adapted to the policy of the institution. Not only TTA, but also scientific products created in its branches are placed on the platform. To date, the number of products placed in all directions is about 6000 and it is possible to use them after passing authorization. These, in turn, are the conditions created for employees, masters and students engaged in scientific work at the institution.

III. CONCLUSION

Summarizing the above information, with the introduction of modern information communication technologies, tIRCoq technology, the mechanism of rapid data exchange and placing information on electronic platforms has led to a change in traditional information exchange.

Firstly, new technologies have accelerated the traditional methods of scientific communication. The massive exchange of verbal information and large experimental data has accelerated significantly. For some scientists in the field of physics and mathematics, it has become a common form of communication to introduce archival data to others interested in the field before publication.

Secondly, the number of important scientific researches is increasing because their work process and results are not required to be published. For example, official papers and technical reports are funded by various financial foundations, research organizations in the field of computer science, and quantum or biotechnology analysts.

Thirdly, as the possibilities of obtaining primary search results in tIRCoq increase, the dependence of information on traditional publication decreases.

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